

PsiNet LAB: Transforming Psychology with Advanced Science for a Deeper Understanding of Human Behavior

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This is an Open Science in Action Story written by its participants to share the initiative in MetaDocencia channels and beyond. To submit your story, please [complete the form](#) (in Spanish).

What is PsiNet LAB?

PsiNet LAB is a psychological research organization dedicated to generating cutting-edge scientific knowledge in Psychology. It is committed to practically applying this knowledge to improve society's mental health and well-being. Through an interdisciplinary and collaborative approach, it integrates diverse perspectives to address urgent and emerging problems. The work ranges from basic research to implementing interventions that promote human well-being and sustainable development. The team uses the latest methodological advances, such as network analysis, multiverse analysis, Bayesian frameworks, machine learning, and Artificial Intelligence (AI), to answer fundamental questions about human behavior based on complexity theory. In addition, it maintains a strong commitment to accessibility and transparency in science, openly sharing its findings to contribute to the collective advancement of knowledge.

Who participate?

PsiNet LAB participants are psychologists who are passionate about science and the dissemination of knowledge. They are committed to rigorous research and applying scientific principles to understand human behavior better. In addition to their interest in psychology, they are dedicated to promoting education and awareness of relevant issues, using their findings to positively influence society and contribute to the advancement of the psychological field. Their commitment to ethics and social responsibility guides their research and outreach activities.

Social networks:

- Facebook: <https://www.facebook.com/psinetlab.of>
- Instagram: <https://www.instagram.com/psinetlab.pe/>
- LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/psinet-lab>
- GitHub: <https://github.com/PsiNet-LAB>
- YouTube: <https://www.youtube.com/@PsiNetLAB>
- TikTok: <https://www.tiktok.com/@psinet.lab>
- Webpage: <https://psinetlab.wordpress.com/>

How does the initiative relate to Open Science?

PsiNet LAB is deeply committed to Open Science, ensuring that the results, codes, and methods are available in accessible repositories such as OSF and GitHub. In addition, the community organizes open classes to disseminate advanced methodologies, allowing more people to benefit from innovative approaches. All the scientific articles are open access, ensuring that the knowledge generated is available to all. PsiNet LAB also collaborates on projects with communities that speak indigenous languages, ensuring that the research is not only inclusive but also respects and values cultural diversity. This open and collaborative approach

allows them to contribute to collective advancement and democratize access to science.

What people does the initiative represent and include?

PsiNet LAB's initiatives encompass a wide variety of populations, including young adults, university students, and older adults, with a recent focus on Quechua speakers. They have not only conducted rigorous research but also organized both virtual and face-to-face outreach activities.

They promote initiatives such as *BienEstar*, dedicated to the dissemination of knowledge and promotion of academic activities for the general population on mental health and its most modern advances; as well as *PsiNet EsCool*, dedicated to bringing scientific training to students and teachers of schools in different regions of Peru from their educational centers.

These activities seek findings and methodologies from different groups, ensuring that everyone has access to information and useful tools to improve their well-being and psychological understanding. Through these efforts, PsiNet LAB seeks to promote inclusion and strengthen the ties between science and the community.

Screenshot of part of the PsiNet LAB members from the cities of Arequipa, Lima, and Huánuco, during a Google Meet meeting. The boxes are divided into a 3x3 matrix. From the top left corner to the top right corner are Milene (Arequipa), Dennis (Lima), and Jefri (Arequipa); from the center-left corner to the center-right are Carlos (Arequipa), Angel (Lima) and Gleni (Arequipa); from the lower left corner to the lower right corner are Alvaro (Lima), Valery (Huánuco) and Marcelo (Arequipa).

Acknowledgments

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